

Political Ecotourism: Lake Sebedang Tourism Object Development Strategy Through Community-Based Tourism

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ABSTRACT

West Kalimantan Province is blessed with a wealth of tourism potential, including Lake Sebedang in Sambas Regency. However, there are complex problems from the political side of ecotourism in it. This research was conducted to analyze the strategy for developing the Sebedang Lake tourist attraction through the concept of community-based tourism from an ecotourism political perspective. The method used is a descriptive qualitative. The data in this research were obtained from interviews and documentation studies. Through this research, a strategy formulation was produced that can support increased development of the Sebedang Lake tourist attraction in harmony with environmental sustainability through community-based tourism, namely the need for synergy between stakeholders and the community as the main actors.

INTRODUCTION

Implementing regional autonomy is a strategic step in making the national reform agenda a success. In this context, regional independence is needed in implementing development. Currently, development does not only rely on the traditional economy as a pillar but also focuses on developing supporting sectors such as tourism. Tourism is a sector that has a positive impact on regional development. It is an important development tool that provides economic, social, and political development in the region.

The tourism sector is a leading sector of the national and regional economy that is growing quite rapidly in Indonesia. This sector is related to several economic, social, political, cultural, regional, and environmental sectors (Drakel, 2020). The development of the tourism sector is one of the efforts to improve the country's economy. Because the tourism potential of an area accelerates multidimensional regional development.

Increased tourism spending has provided economic recovery and increased employment opportunities that support community welfare (Boz & Serçek, 2016). The many tourist attractions in Indonesia attract visitors, both local and foreign tourists. Tourism's contribution to the economy generates additional local income and employment opportunities, thus becoming the largest foreign exchange contributor and absorber of labor. Foreign exchange earnings from the Indonesian tourism sector will reach US\$4.26 billion in 2022. This value has jumped by 769.39% compared to the previous year (Widi, 2022). This can be seen in the following graph.

Figure 1. Foreign Exchange Income from the Indonesian Tourism Sector in 2013 – 2023

Source: Widi, 2022

A country's opportunities to participate in important social, economic, political, and cultural events will depend on its ability to ensure the sustainability of its tourism industry. Therefore, a nation must be serious about managing its tourism industry if it wants to have a positive impact on the environment, society, and tourism sustainability. This will also make the region more attractive to the nation as a whole (Mustapa, 2019). Local governments play an important role in promoting sustainable tourism development.

West Kalimantan Province has natural, artistic, and cultural potential that can be developed as a tourism product by the local government. Sebedang Lake is a natural tourist attraction that is full of historical and ecological value and is the mainstay of Sambas Regency natural tourism which is supported by Sambas Regency Regional Regulation Number 5 of 2016 concerning the Sambas Regency Tourism Development Master Plan for 2016-2036.

This lake is located in Sebawi District which has a natural panorama complete with tropical forests, giving the impression of being calm, shady, and refreshing. In this area, there are various facilities such as gazebos, prayer rooms, cafes, and villas. Sebedang Lake is also used as a source of raw water for the Tebas, Semparuk, and Sebawi units managed by the Tirta Muare Ulakan Regional Drinking Water Company, Sambas Regency. Apart from that, the hills of Lake Sebedang are used as a Chinese burial place. Some people use Sebedang Lake as their place for fish farming as can be seen in the following picture.

Figure 2. Panorama of Sebedang Lake Tourist Objects
(a) Gate, (b) Welcoming Spot, (c) Raw Water Intake, (d) Fish Pond
Source: Researcher documentation, 2023

Sebedang Lake, which is located in two villages, namely Sempalai Sebedang Village and Sepuk Tanjung Village, is managed by various stakeholders such as the community, private sector, and government, and also has a Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis), namely Pokdarwis Paggong Sebedang. The Lake Sebedang Nature Tourism Village was included in the 6 tourist villages in Sambas Regency and was nominated for the 2023 Indonesian Tourism Village Award. However, the Lake Sebedang Nature Tourism Village

was not successful in continuing its journey to the Top 75 ADWIs in West Kalimantan 2023. The Tourism Villages that passed this stage were from West Kalimantan Province, namely the Jeruju Besar Tourism Village, Kubu Raya Regency, and the Cipta Karya Tourism Village, Bengkayang Regency (Putri, 2023).

The number of visitors, both local and foreign tourists, increased from Christmas Day to New Year, recorded from 24 December 2022 to 2 January 2023, reaching 10,199 tourists (Maksum, 2023). This success cannot be separated from the Lake Sebedang area which has long been known as a tourist attraction in Sambas Regency for both local and foreign tourists. However, the lack of supervision and attention from the district government in managing and developing the tourism potential of Lake Sebedang means that this area is still not managed optimally and professionally (Megawati, Mulki, & Yuniarti, 2019).

Apart from that, problems related to environmental sustainability in the Lake Sebedang tourist attraction area also face quite complex challenges. As stated by the Director of the Regional Public Drinking Water Company Tirta Muare Ulakan, Sambas Regency, Arpandi S.P., the development of the Sebedang Lake tourist attraction directly affects the quality standards of Sebedang Lake water, making it a challenge for the sustainability of ecotourism (Media Kalbar News, 2022).

Therefore, Sebedang Lake requires management that is by the five principles of natural tourism management, namely: (1) preserving ecosystem functions, (2) preserving natural tourist attraction objects, (3) socio-cultural sustainability, (4) satisfaction, safety, and visitor comfort, and (5) economic benefits (Badan Standardisasi Nasional, 2020). This is also in line with the political principle of ecotourism which balances the regional economy with environmental sustainability through the role of the state and society as part of the synergy between tourism actors.

These various problems make it a challenge for all stakeholders to work together to improve the development of the Sebedang Lake tourist attraction (Zhan, 2017). Based on these problems, this research was conducted to examine the Politics of Ecotourism: Strategy for Developing Lake Sebedang Tourism Objects through Community-Based Tourism to support the development of Lake Sebedang's tourism potential.

Previous studies related to tourism management from an ecotourism political perspective have found the relationship between ecotourism politics and global networks that include donors and international travel agents, as well as their relationship as a path to development (Duffy, 2008). The novelty of this research lies in the research focus, namely analyzing the strategy for developing the Sebedang Lake tourist attraction through the concept of community-based tourism with an ecotourism political perspective.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Community-Based Tourism and Political Ecotourism Perspective

Tourism is an inseparable part of human life, especially regarding social and economic activities. According to Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism, tourism is a variety of tourist activities.

Management of this sector is not only the task of state actors but the task of multi-actors including society (Zhan, 2023). It aims to involve the community in aspects of tourism, from planning to active participation (Zivrali, 2022). Community-based tourism seeks to support communities through tourism activities and aims to offer tourists authentic local experiences.

The community-based tourism concept is a tourism concept that takes into account aspects of environmental, social, and cultural sustainability. Community-based tourism is human-oriented and supports and maintains natural and cultural resources. There are five main aspects in the development of this concept as can be seen in the following image.

Figure 3. Main Aspects in Community-Based Tourism Development
Source: Olahkarsa, 2023

Apart from that, there are three main principles in the tourism development planning strategy in the Community-Based Tourism concept. First, active participation from the community in decision-making. Second, there are benefits felt directly by local communities. Third, providing tourism education to local communities (Sunaryo, 2013). These three things provide optimization and benefits for tourism development.

The advantages of developing tourism using this concept include the fact that it can produce quite a large increase in tourist visits, exchanges, and the purchasing power of local products and crafts through unlimited creative idea innovation. Important for the tourism industry, including Community-Based Tourism, is sustainability (Ahsani, Wulandari, Dinata, Azmi, & Fathani, 2022). The concept of sustainability needs to continue to be implemented in stages to produce local community-based tourism that involves a lot of synergy between stakeholders. Sustainable tourism development is an integrated and organized effort to develop the quality of tourism activities by managing the provision, development, utilization, and maintenance of resources in a sustainable manner. This is in line with the concept of ecotourism politics.

Ecotourism politics is a combination of political science and ecological science in looking at the same object, namely tourism. Ecotourism politics is a rapidly growing niche market in one of the world's largest industries, supported by state political policies. Community-based ecotourism politics needs to realize that the community as stakeholders is at the heart of tourism management (Ghaderi & Henderson, 2012).

There are several political issues involved in ecotourism, and it is not a technical, neutral, or unproblematic approach to complex questions around development or sustainability. The politics of ecotourism is supported as a sustainable development strategy by a variety of local, national, and global actors ranging from NGOs to bilateral relations, many of whom claim that it is a politically neutral strategy. However, the politics of ecotourism is evident at various scales and levels (Duffy, 2008). At the national level, ecotourism politics requires national policies that support infrastructure development and environmental sustainability to attract tourists from abroad.

Through this political concept of ecotourism, society and the government together create a system where the education, culture, economy, and environmental protection sectors can work hand in hand. The political concept of ecotourism, which has rapid opportunities, is also considered to still have many shortcomings from a juridical perspective in implementing its policies. These include, among other things, the lack of harmonization of laws and regulations that mandate the existence of ecotourism and community knowledge and participation which is still considered lacking (Wijayanto, Najicha, Agfianto, & Nugroho, 2022).

Ecotourism politics develops and grows in a period of political transition which is strongly influenced by time and space. Political studies on ecotourism have identified three key players in tourism development, namely the state, society, and the market (Prasiasa, 2022). Therefore, ecotourism politics is focused both on the environment outside the community environment and on aspects that include the community environment.

METHODOLOGY

The method used is a descriptive research method with a qualitative approach. Descriptive research is intended to describe symptoms, events, and occurrences that are occurring at present where the researcher tries to describe them as they are (Murdiyanto, 2020). With a qualitative descriptive approach, analysis of the data obtained is expressed in the form of an explanation or description of the situation or conditions studied in the form of a narrative description.

In this research, the selection of informants used a purposive sampling method to (1) Head of the Sambas Regency Tourism, Youth and Sports Office, (2) Head of the Tirta Muare Ulakan Drinking Water Regional Public Company, Sambas Regency, (3) Chair of the Tourism Awareness Group Paggong Sebedang, and (4) Chairman of the Genpi of Sambas Regency.

The data in this research were obtained from interviews and documentation studies. Interviews were conducted using in-depth interview

techniques with predetermined key informants. The documentation study was carried out by collecting several articles, research, news archives, and reports regarding the development of the Sebedang Lake tourist attraction from an environmental and political perspective.

RESEARCH RESULT

Development of Sebedang Lake Ecotourism in Sambas Regency

Sambas Regency in West Kalimantan Province offers various types of tourism. Currently, it has been recorded that Sambas Regency has 71 tourist attraction locations which are divided into marine tourism, cultural tourism, special interest tourism, natural tourism, and so on. Marine tourism is a type of tourism related to activities around waters, such as the sea, beaches, and islands. This includes activities such as diving, snorkeling, sailing, fishing, and enjoying the beauty of the underwater world. Marine tourism can also involve visits to marine parks, conservation areas, and coasts.

Talking about the mainstay tourist attractions in Sambas Regency, one of them is Sebedang Lake. Since 2008 and before, the direction of development of Lake Sebedang has been towards the concept of ecotourism, which then began to be pursued regarding its spatial planning, especially considering its position adjacent to the Tirta Muare Regional Drinking Water Company Ulakan Sambas, Arpandi, S.P. also revealed that Sebedang Lake has been conceptualized as environmentally based and sustainable ecotourism and efforts are being made to ensure that it can continue to run side by side with clean water sources.

Regarding the development of the Sebedang Lake tourist attraction, there is currently a lot of improvement which can be seen from the increasingly organized Paggong Tourism Awareness Group of Sempalai Sebedang Village for the 2021-2026 period which is currently chaired by Ardy Sanjaya, S.I.P. The well-organized tourism management of Lake Sebedang is producing results. Based on the results of interviews with Ardy Sanjaya, S.I.P., it is known that during the one-week Eid al-Fitr 2023 holiday, the total number of visitors seen from the entrance tickets was 24,185 people consisting of 10,447 motorbikes and 688 cars. This positive thing shows the increasing public interest in Lake Sebedang as a tourist attraction.

During the Covid-19 pandemic, many tourist attractions experienced a decline in visitors, but the number of visitors to Sebedang Lake remained stable. After the Covid-19 pandemic ended, many tourist attractions closed and no longer operated, such as Riam Sajingan and others, according to Syopian Asthauri, S.E. What caused Lake Sebedang to survive during the Covid-19 pandemic and after the Covid-19 pandemic was that access to Lake Sebedang was easy (accessible) and the image of Lake Sebedang as a typical Sambas tourist attraction has been known from generation to generation.

Even amid limited tourism activities due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the Paggong Sebedang Tourism Awareness Group succeeded in holding an event with strict protocol standards. Apart from that, the existing cafes have also

succeeded in obtaining health standards from the ministry. Tourism management at Sebedang Lake has implemented the Peduli Protect QR Barcode.

The Paggong Sebedang Tourism Awareness Group, as the community that manages the Lake Sebedang tourist attraction, has won the Land and Building Tax award in 2023 for compliance in fulfilling local tax obligations through all events and entrance ticket activities at Lake Sebedang. Withdrawal of entrance tickets for visitors to Sebedang Lake cannot be carried out freely, but according to the Special Tourism Tax Regional Regulations which are focused only when activities or entertainment are held at tourist locations with a tax of 15%.

This is because in Sambas Regency there is no special tourism tax. So, the tax used at the Sebedang Lake tourist attraction is the Entertainment Tax, meaning that in every tourist area where an entrance ticket fee is charged, it is mandatory to provide entertainment, for example, musical entertainment from bands, solo organs, and attractions. If there is no entertainment facilitated by the committee for the tourist area then the Regional Entertainment Regulations do not apply (Sambas News, 2023). Apart from that, every cafe and canteen in Lake Sebedang is also included in the 10% restaurant tax. Thus, the contribution of tourism from Lake Sebedang greatly contributes to efforts to increase Regional Original Income.

Potential and Challenges in the Development of Sebedang Lake Ecotourism

The Sebedang Lake area is indirectly divided into 3 divisions. First, in the northern part of Sepok Tanjung Village. Second, in the southern part which is the entrance gate to Sempalai Sebedang. Third, land owned by the regional government in Taman Istana Putri which is currently in the development process. Based on the results of an interview with Syopian Asthauri, S.E., at Sebedang Lake there are also available locations for camping. Sebedang Lake itself, based on the 2016–2036 Sambas Regency Tourism Development Master Plan, is included in the tourism group which consists of Sambas, Sajad, Sebawi, Sejangkung, and Subah Districts. Lake Sebedang is a popular tourist destination and its natural beauty is supported by its condition. The mountains that surround the Lake Sebedang area, one of which is Mount Amor, which is located on the southern edge of the lake, are another attraction that adds to the natural beauty of Lake Sebedang.

The second entrance to Lake Sebedang, located in Sepuk Tanjung Village, is where visitors can access Mount Amor which offers a clear view of Lake Sebedang. Apart from Mount Amor, there is a small island called Pulau Panjang which is located in the middle of Lake Sebedang, adding to the natural beauty of the lake. Sebedang Lake is surrounded by tropical rainforests, making it a fertile area and has clear water. The existence (existence) of the Lake Sebedang tourist area can be seen in the following picture.

Figure 4. Existing Sebedang Lake Tourism

Source: Dinas Pariwisata, Kepemudaan dan Olahraga Kabupaten Sambas, 2021

Lake Sebedang in Sambas Regency has ecotourism potential which attracts visitors starting of its natural beauty because Lake Sebedang is surrounded by tropical forests and stunning natural scenery. The surrounding forests provide habitat for a variety of unique flora and fauna. The ecotourism potential here includes trekking, bird watching, and other activities that allow visitors to enjoy the natural beauty that has not been polluted.

Apart from that, Lake Sebedang has the potential for biodiversity because the area around Lake Sebedang is home to various species of rare plants and animals. This creates opportunities for the development of ecotourism that educates visitors about conservation and biodiversity. Sebedang Lake is also an important source of fresh water, and this lake ecosystem can be used as a place for various ecotourism activities such as boat trips, fishing, and observing aquatic animals. Visitors can learn about ecology and the importance of maintaining water quality and lake ecosystems. Thus, Sebedang Lake and its surroundings have the potential to become a conservation area to protect rare species and natural habitats. Sustainable ecotourism development can help in financing and managing these conservation efforts.

Ecotourism at Lake Sebedang which also includes interaction with local communities and an understanding of the traditional communities that inhabit the area. This can involve touring local villages, understanding customs, and sampling traditional cuisine. In this way, Sebedang Lake can become a center for ecological and conservation education and research. Universities and research institutions can work with local authorities to conduct scientific studies and environmental education in these areas.

According to Uray Rizki Suhendra, General Chair of Genpi Sambas, he said that various programs support ecotourism, including lake tourism by boat, so that visitors can travel along the lake by boat while seeing the beautiful panorama around the lake and seeing the mountains. There is also a jogging track, inviting all levels of society to take part in this event, apart from exercising, all participants can see the beautiful panorama of Lake Sebedang.

So, it is important to create a sustainable tourism infrastructure and maintain a balance between nature conservation and tourism development. This involves active involvement of local communities, environmental protection, and promotion of sustainability in the development of ecotourism in Sebedang Lake. Then it can be concluded that Lake Sebedang's ecotourism potential includes (1) biodiversity, (2) exotic natural scenery, (3) the presence of forests and potential conservation areas, and (4) cultural and historical values that are in line with ecotourism conservation efforts.

Currently, several challenges need to be faced for the development of Sebedang Lake Ecotourism. First, there is a need to understand that people who carry out activities or who provide tourism activities are not yet in line with the existing program of the Tirta Muare Ulakan Regional Public Company for Drinking Water, Sambas Regency. Considering that the Regional Public Company for Drinking Water, Tirta Muare Ulakan, Sambas Regency is present side by side with the Lake Sebedang tourist location, the community feels that the water quality is affected.

The results of this research found that the local community had expressed aspirations requesting that the Tourism Office make provisions or a radius regarding tourist areas. Regarding this issue, a meeting was then held facilitated by the village and community inviting the Tirta Muare Ulakan Regional Public Company for Drinking Water, Sambas Regency; Sambas Regency Tourism, Youth and Sports Office; Sambas Regency Public Works and Spatial Planning Service; and the Public Housing, Settlement Areas, and Environment Service of Sambas Regency.

The results of the meetings held include one from the Public Housing, Settlement Areas, and Environment Service of Sambas Regency which revealed that tourism activities at Lake Sebedang can continue to be carried out by prioritizing sustainable tourism. For example, if there are canoes operating on Sebedang Lake, using an engine is not permitted because, from an environmental perspective, there is concern that oil will pollute the lake. So, if a canoe uses paddles, it is allowed to operate on Sebedang Lake.

Apart from that, Lake Sebedang is located in two villages. In the Sebedang Lake area in Sepuk Tanjung Village, there is a problem that is overshadowing the development of ecotourism, namely the Chinese cemetery. This is because when it rains, water from the cemetery will enter the lake. Meanwhile, Chinese burials usually use materials such as formaldehyde which has the potential to pollute the aquatic ecosystem in lakes. According to Syopian Asthauri, S.E., regarding this problem, a meeting was held between the Public Works and Spatial Planning Department of Sambas Regency and the community who requested that drainage be made so that rainwater from the Chinese burial area in the hills around Lake Sebedang can be channeled to the area. other.

Seeing these things, the community must be involved in managing natural resources around the lake, such as waste management, water conservation, and keeping the lake clean. The community can be involved in reforestation programs, cleaning the environment around the lake, and

ensuring the sustainability of the ecosystem. In this case, the community can be an agent of change in increasing awareness of ecotourism sustainability.

Based on interviews with informants, the challenges in developing Lake Sebedang ecotourism are then explained in the following chart.

Figure 5. Challenges in the Development of Sebedang Lake Ecotourism
Source: Processed by researchers, 2023

Community participation is the main thing needed for the development of a tourist area. In developing ecotourism areas, community participation can be realized by complying with existing regional regulations in the Sebedang Lake tourist area. This specifically includes the construction of cafes so that they do not enter the body or shores of the lake which threatens to pollute the water of Lake Sebedang. Community participation is also manifested in the form of maintaining the cleanliness of tourist areas. Apart from that, the community must be involved in the planning process for ecotourism development. Community opinions, needs, and concerns must be heard to ensure that ecotourism development in Lake Sebedang takes local interests into account.

Apart from that, there is also the role of the younger generation through the Generasi Pesona Indonesia (Genpi), which is a youth community that cares about tourism and is overseen by the Tourism Office. The Genpi Community of Sambas Regency has an important role in developing tourist destinations in Sambas Regency. This was stated by the Chairman of Genpi Sambas, Uray Rizki Suhendra. According to him, Genpi Sambas members care about the existence of tourist destinations in Sambas Regency, especially Sebedang Lake which has a panoramic view that is beautiful to the eye. Genpi's role is of course also to participate in protecting and preserving the surrounding area and preserving the culture of the local community. This provides an opportunity for the surrounding community to improve their welfare.

Apart from that, tourists who visit Lake Sebedang in particular can support ecotourism sustainability. The behavior of visiting tourists should reflect the principles of *Sapta Pesona*, namely safe, orderly, clean, cool, beautiful, friendly, and memorable. By following the principles of *Sapta Pesona*, tourists can become agents of change who support the sustainability of ecotourism in Lake Sebedang, while still enjoying the natural and cultural charm offered by this destination.

Another important thing is the synergy of regulations and programs between stakeholders. It needs harmonization with the Sambas Regency Regional Regulation Number 17 of 2015 concerning the Sambas Regency Spatial Planning Plan for 2015–2035 and the Drinking Water Supply System Master Plan 2015–2035 which also states that Lake Sebedang is also a source of raw water. Therefore, joint action between stakeholders regarding the restructuring and reintroduction of the Sebedang Lake tourist area needs to be carried out immediately. This includes arranging buildings and cafes so that they do not enter the body or shores of Lake Sebedang. Apart from that, the radius is also determined so as not to pollute the water of Lake Sebedang.

Regarding optimizing waste management in the Sebedang Lake area, various parties still need to pay attention. The cleanliness of the Lake Sebedang tourist attraction area also requires monitoring and additional temporary storage facilities so that waste in the area can be managed well and does not threaten the environmental sustainability of the Lake Sebedang ecotourism area. According to H. Subhan Nur, member of the Regional People's Representative Council of West Kalimantan Province (Electoral District 4 Sambas Regency), rubbish in the Lake Sebedang tourist area always piles up during the Eid al-Fitr season as the number of tourists increases (Sambas Times, 2023). Currently, there is a Temporary Waste Storage Site in the Sebedang Lake area, but the behavior of the public and tourists still needs to be educated so that they can keep Sebedang Lake clean of rubbish.

Figure 6. Temporary Garbage Storage Site at Lake Sebedang
Source: Researcher documentation, 2023

Currently, other facilities that support ecotourism at Sebedang Lake also have trash cans from the Sambas Regency Regional Government. Then, the Sambas Regency Public Housing, Settlement Areas, and Environment Service have also provided trash containers and tosses for transporting waste. The

Regional Public Company for Drinking Water, Tirta Muare Ulakan, Sambas Regency also provides grass-cutting machines and trash cans.

Furthermore, Sebedang Lake is not only used for ecotourism but also develops oil palm plantations there. This has a significant impact on the environment and ecosystem in the region, such as decreasing water absorption because the natural tropical forests that previously existed were then replaced by oil palm plantations. The following is a portrait of an oil palm plantation adjacent to the Lake Sebedang tourist area.

Figure 7. Palm Oil Plantations in the Sebedang Lake Area
Source: Researcher documentation, 2023

Massive oil palm plantations in the area around the Lake Sebedang tourist area also have the potential to eliminate natural habitat for local flora and fauna and cause biodiversity loss. Not to mention the use of pesticides and chemicals in palm oil farming can pollute the water around the lake. Palm oil plantation waste that enters the water flow around Lake Sebedang has the potential to cause pollution to the water ecosystem. Thus, environmental conservation and protection efforts are needed to mitigate the negative impacts of oil palm plantations. Apart from oil palm plantations, there are also mining activities around the Lake Sebedang tourist area. Sebedang Lake itself is also an artificial lake created by Chinese mining in ancient times. The mining to date can be seen in the following image.

Figure 8. Mining Locations Around the Sebedang Lake Area
Source: Researcher documentation, 2023

Currently, mining activities are still carried out by the company with a class C excavation classification, which takes sand, gravel, river rock, and landfill as a source. In general, class C mineral mining entrepreneurs carry out mining activities using heavy equipment which has the potential to create large holes from excavations that are quite deep (3–4 meters) and if these excavations are not reclaimed it can result in damage to the surrounding environment.

Even though it is legal, mining has the potential to disrupt natural ecosystems, reduce biodiversity, and trigger soil erosion which directly affects the water quality in Lake Sebedang. Therefore, strict supervision, well-enforced regulations, and a sustainable approach to mining are needed to minimize these negative impacts and ensure the sustainability of ecotourism and the lives of local communities in the Sebedang Lake area.

Sebedang Lake is also used by the local community as a place for fish cages. There are several types of fish cultivated in Sebedang Lake, such as goldfish and tilapia which are cultivated in floating net cages. Apart from that, people also cultivate toman, snakehead, and fish cage "keramba" using a fishing system using nets or fishing rods. On average, fish species have high potential, calculated from the total price of fish sold from the catch of these fish per kilogram, which can reach IDR 50,000.00 (Agam, Merdekawati, Maryono, Yunita, & Reksi, 2022). The benefits of fish cage management imply the need to develop the potential of natural resources in line with the concept of ecotourism

so that they can be utilized optimally without damaging the environment so that the sustainability of Lake Sebedang can be felt by future generations.

Lastly, the existence of a Chinese burial area around Lake Sebedang has the potential to pollute the water in Lake Sebedang. The burial area of the Chinese Foundation existed before the tourism service managed tourism at Lake Sebedang. This potential comes from preservatives used for funeral needs such as formalin. Confirmation from the funeral director that currently the preservative used is no longer formalin but has used a cooling agent. However, it is still necessary to monitor quality standards and ecological conditions around Lake Sebedang for these preservatives.

Figure 9. Chinese Cemetery in the Lake Sebedang Area
Source: Researcher documentation, 2023

DISCUSSION

A key component of community-based tourism is ensuring that local communities have actively participated in current tourism development. Two aspects of community involvement in tourism are the first, decision-making, and the second, namely the distribution of benefits. Therefore, there are three main principles of community-based tourism development planning strategies, namely (1) involving community members in decision-making; (2) ensuring that local communities obtain benefits from tourism; and (3) providing tourism education for local communities (Sunaryo, 2013).

Empowering local communities in locations that are tourist attractions through tourism business activities is a development model that is currently receiving a lot of attention from various groups and will be an important agenda in future tourism development. So, to ensure that tourism development runs well and is well managed, the most basic thing to do is facilitate the broad involvement of the local community in the development process and maximize the value of social and economic benefits from tourism activities for the local community.

Local communities have an equally important position as stakeholders in tourism development apart from the government and private industry,

including those currently being promoted at the Sebedang Lake tourist attraction. Apart from the local community, community involvement is also realized through the Tourism Awareness Group. The involvement of the Paggong Sebedang Tourism Awareness Group in supporting the management and development of Lake Sebedang ecotourism can be said to be very progressive. Not only managing tourism, but Pokdarwis has also coordinated with the Sambas Regency Public Housing, Settlement, and Environmental Services Department which supports Lake Sebedang as ecotourism. As a follow-up to this coordination, measurements were made of which parts of the zone could be utilized by the community at Lake Sebedang.

This is very important to do considering that the existence of Lake Sebedang is a complex matter of use for the surrounding community. Regarding the raw water from Lake Sebedang itself, it is currently still in a usable condition. The Regional Public Company for Drinking Water Tirta Muare Ulakan, Sambas Regency routinely tests the quality of raw water in Pontianak and I can still say that the results of this test are adequate.

Apart from that, the water distributed to communities that receive water supply from Sebedang Lake has gone through a processing process. This treatment is carried out at the Makrampai Village Water Treatment Plant, Tebas District with a capacity of 90 liters per second to serve 3 sub-districts, namely Sebawi, Tebas, and Semparuk. The addition of chemicals to neutralize acidic substances in the raw water with chlorine and the use of alum to clean the water from peat or a mixture of soil in the water at levels that allow the process to be carried out.

Furthermore, according to Syopian Asthauri, S.E. from the Sambas Regency Tourism, Youth and Sports Office, during the Covid-19 pandemic, many tourist attractions experienced a decline in visitors, but visitors at Sebedang Lake remained stable. Then after the Covid-19 pandemic was over, many tourist attractions closed and no longer operated, for example, Riam Sajingan, but this was not the case with Lake Sebedang. This is because the Sebedang Lake tourist attraction has an image as a typical Sambas Regency tourist attraction that has been known for generations.

In the development of Lake Sebedang ecotourism, there are no actors who can just walk alone. Therefore, synergy between stakeholders is very necessary with the community as the main pillar to jointly advance the Sebedang Lake tourist destination, including the promotion aspect through online and offline media which is increasingly developing in this era, creating various events to attract visitors. This is stated in the three principles of tourism, namely something to see which is manifested in supporting tourist attractions, something to do which is manifested in attractions, and something to buy which is manifested in products such as typical souvenirs and so on (Budiani, et al, 2018).

Apart from that, two points are added, namely something to empower and something to sustain (Rahayu, Dewi, & Fitriana, 2016). Community-based tourism is then supported by ecotourism politics which is implemented by ensuring regulations and program synergy between stakeholders as well as

ensuring community aspirations and participation in the development of Sebedang Lake ecotourism. This was done to resolve challenges in developing Lake Sebedang ecotourism. The community can be considered politically empowered when all community members feel fairly represented and when they have a channel to convey their concerns regarding tourism development, in this case, Lake Sebedang ecotourism. Community empowerment in ecotourism politics emphasizes the increasing need to give communities control over tourism development through active voting rights in planning processes that are aligned with ecological or environmental sustainability.

The focus of community-based tourism is on the quality of life of the community around the tourist attraction so that it can provide maximum benefits for the tourist attraction in terms of economic, environmental, and socio-cultural sustainability. The community-based tourism approach aims to create a mutually beneficial relationship between tourism and local communities, by ensuring that the benefits of the tourism industry are distributed fairly and sustainably to local communities while preserving culture and the environment. So, the community-based tourism strategy from an ecotourism political perspective supports the optimization of Lake Sebedang ecotourism development carried out by aspects of community-based tourism itself as illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 10. Community-Based Tourism Strategy in an Ecotourism Political Perspective Supports Optimization of Lake Sebedang Ecotourism Development
 Source: Processed by Researchers, 2023

The quality and quantity of community empowerment will be directly proportional to the impact of ecotourism. If a positive impact is felt, an empowered society will invest more in it. Meanwhile, if negative impacts are felt, it depends on factors such as the extent of their empowerment and opportunities to take alternative actions. This research also shows that by

prioritizing the community as the main actor in developing Lake Sebedang ecotourism, the community itself will become more aware of their rights to support the development of Lake Sebedang ecotourism which is not only of destination value but also has social, economic, and cultural value for the community. local community.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This research found several challenges in developing ecotourism in Lake Sebedang, including at least eight things, namely the participation of the local community which still needs to increase its awareness of the sustainability of the Lake Sebedang tourist area, the behavior of tourists whose awareness needs to be increased so that it is by the values of *Sapta Pesona*, the synergy of regulations and programs between stakeholders so that there is no lack of regulations and no overlapping or even conflicting programs in the Lake Sebedang area, optimizing waste management, the need to anticipate the impact of oil palm plantations, the need to anticipate the impact of mining, the need to anticipate the impact of fish cages, and the need for cemetery management Chinese who do not affect the water quality and ecology of Lake Sebedang.

In the development of Lake Sebedang ecotourism, synergy between stakeholders is very necessary with the community as the main actor. This is stated in the principle, namely, something to see which is realized in supporting tourist attractions, something to do which is realized by attractions, something to buy which is realized in by-products such as typical souvenirs and so on, something to empower, and something to sustain which is implemented through ecotourism politics by ensuring regulations and program synergy between stakeholders as well as ensuring community aspirations and participation in the development of Sebedang Lake ecotourism. This was done to resolve challenges in developing Lake Sebedang ecotourism.

Based on the conclusions of this research, several suggestions can be made to improve the development of Lake Sebedang ecotourism, the first of which is increasing public awareness. This needs to be implemented through education and outreach programs to the community around Sebedang Lake about the importance of environmental preservation and sustainability of this tourist attraction. This can be done through campaigns, training, and active involvement in conservation programs initiated by tourism-related stakeholders such as the society itself, Tourism Awareness Group, *Generasi Pesona Indonesia (Genpi)* community, government agencies, non-government agencies, media, academics, and business actors.

Apart from that, efforts are needed to increase tourist awareness about the principles of ecotourism, regarding the importance of respecting the environment, local culture, and sustainability while enjoying Sebedang Lake tourism which can be provided through packaging tour packages or tourist facilities. Then, synergies between related parties such as government, land owners, economic actors, and local communities need to be harmonized. This aims to create clear regulations, without overlap, and maintain the continuity of programs that support the preservation of Lake Sebedang. Emphasizing the

importance of managing ecotourism by paying attention to sustainability in existing regulations and programs, while ensuring active community participation in decision-making regarding the development of tourist attractions.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

This research has limitations, namely the limited scope of this research, so a broader analysis is needed. Apart from that, in the future there will also be a need for data obtained from stakeholders in the regulatory sector as well as sources from the surrounding community and those related to the research locus.

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